

Nature, the Elixir of Life: A Critique of Rahul Varma's *Land Where the Trees Talk*

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Abstract:

This paper delves into the intricacies of Rahul Varma's literary work, "Land Where the Trees Talk," critically examining the thematic underpinnings that explore the profound relationship between humanity and nature. Varma's narrative unfolds within a context where the natural world is not merely a backdrop but an active participant in the unfolding drama. The paper navigates through the author's portrayal of nature as a dynamic force, asserting its agency and engaging in a profound dialogue with the human characters. The critique employs a multi-dimensional approach, encompassing environmental philosophy, cultural studies, and literary analysis. By scrutinizing Varma's treatment of nature, the paper aims to unravel the symbolic significance attributed to the natural elements within the narrative. It explores the author's use of language, symbolism, and narrative techniques to convey a nuanced understanding of the symbiotic relationship between humanity and the environment. Furthermore, the paper delves into the implications of Varma's narrative choices in the context of contemporary ecological discourses. It scrutinizes how "Land Where the Trees Talk" contributes to the ongoing dialogue surrounding environmental ethics, sustainability, and the urgent need for a harmonious coexistence between humanity and the natural world.

Key Words: environmental preservation, sustainable development, ecological sabotage

Mother Earth is a goddess, venerated by indigenous peoples. Mother Earth is much more than the soil we walk on. It is the wind, the fire, the water, the element that we breathe and that sustains life and prosperity. Edia López

But surely, surely, when a wrong thing has been done, and you feel it, to suppress your resentment and to stifle protest is to let evil grow unchecked. Civilization and humanity call for the free expression of one's resentment. Rajaji

In his essay "The Tree Speaks," C. Rajagopalachari, a fervent proponent of nature, emphasises the moral obligation of humanity to speak out against unjust deeds. Rajaji's statements likely sparked the artistic inspiration of theatrical artist Rahul Varma, who passionately advocates for social justice. Varma, an Indian author in Canada, has gained significant recognition for exposing numerous societal injustices that are concealed within society. The preservation of nature is crucial as the widespread destruction of the environment

has become prevalent in contemporary times. Varma feels profound anguish upon witnessing the widespread destruction and devastation of the diverse manifestations of nature in the pursuit of human growth under the guise of advancement. His words possess the ability to spark flames and awaken the environmental awareness that has intentionally been concealed within the depths of their hearts. Glen Love, in his essay, “Revaluing Nature: Toward an Ecological Criticism” states, “nature oriented literature offers a needed corrective to our narrowly anthropocentric view of life, nature writing shows regard for the non-human and privileges “eco-consciousness” over “ego-consciousness” (205).

Colonizers, in their mad rush over name, fame and material prosperity conveniently forget that human life is ephemeral. By hook or crook or by fair or foul means they accomplish their goal of colonization. Compassion, benevolence, humanity and fellow feeling have become anachronisms as they transform the colonized soil into “a darkling plain/swept with confused alarms of struggle and flight” (35-36). The so-called denizens of the brave new e-world lacerate the Native souls by grabbing their land and its pristine environment. Nature is part and parcel of Native Canadian life and the Whites with their cold-blooded strategies destroy and pollute Mother Earth in the name of advancement and globalization. They plundered, looted and exploited the natural resources of the Native soil that resulted in environmental colonialism, one of the well-designed ploys of the colonizers. Concepción defines environmental colonization thus:

Environmental colonialism was the consequence of the technology that had been located on the island, which consumed a great deal of energy and generated high levels of contamination. The problem is that those renewable resources that have been damaged and overused are essential not only for production activities but also for all forms of life. Therefore, what is at stake is biological survival as well as economic survival. This policy may be considered a new form of subordination and oppression. (128)

Varma’s full-length play *Land Where the Trees Talk* mirrors the unheard anguish of the Native people of Canada under the British yoke. The sons of the soil grew up in the beloved lap of Mother Earth, worshipping and adoring each and every facet of nature. The speech of the Native American Chief Seattle highlights the eco-centric life of the aboriginals:

Every part of this earth is sacred to my people. Every shining pine needle, every sandy shore, every mist in the dark woods, every meadow, every humming insect. . . . We are part of the earth and it is part of us. The perfumed flowers are our sisters. The bear, the deer, the great eagle, these are our brothers. The shining water that moves in the streams and rivers is not water, but the blood of our ancestors. The rivers are our brothers. They quench our thirst. The wind that gave our grandfather his first breath also receives his last sigh. This we know the earth does not belong to man, man belongs to earth. (qtd. in Gore 159)

The 1984 Union Carbide disaster in Bhopal is the inspiration for the play. Varma correlates the Quebec incident with Bhopal tragedy. In 1984 in Bhopal, Union Carbide's pesticide plant blew up, and deadly contaminous fumes engulfed the city. Varma poignantly states, "small children fell like flies, and men and women vainly scurried for safety only to collapse, breathless and blinded by the gas." In the tragedy 5000 were dead, 80,000 disabled and more than 2, 00,000 were injured and uprooted. Human race had to pay the price for progress and development.

Varma's play delves into the issue of Native land rights in the context of growing environmental consciousness, questioning whether we are preserving the earth for future generations or taking it away from them. Varma refers to environmental injustice as 'Ecotage' or 'Ecological Sabotage'. The James Bay hydro-electric project, conceived by the White imperialists, had a detrimental impact on the Native population, leading to the destruction of their eco-system through deforestation and the contamination of waterways with mercury. Quebec has seized vast portions of Native territory near James Bay, an area larger than France, for the purpose of hydroelectric production. James Bay people are afflicted with mercury poisoning following the initial stage of the operation. Colonialism has disrupted the ecological equilibrium of the indigenous world. The government of Quebec has deprived the Native people of their land and its resources by forcefully implementing the James Bay Hydro project. Although the hydro project has generated revenue for the government of Quebec, it has also forcibly relocated and displaced the Indigenous population, rendering them refugees within their own territory. The Indigenous population is being deprived of political authority and they are the primary recipients of the project's negative consequences.

The Megawatt project symbolises the indifferent and dehumanising behaviour of the White population towards the Indigenous people. Furthermore, it exemplifies the environmental devastation produced by the dominant ethnic group. The Prime Minister commends the project, since he believes it would mitigate the land's economic problems. He envisions a novel realm and highlights the accomplishments of the territory, including the construction of 200 dams and dikes, the utilisation of half a million tonnes of concrete, the creation of 200 million cubic metres of reservoir, the establishment of a 1500 km long road, bar and airport, as well as attracting investors from all parts of the globe. Only a few years ago, this land was unexplored and inhabited by only a handful of trappers and hunters. Currently, it generates a hydroelectric power capacity of 10,000 megawatts (70).

The Prime Minister is not bothered about the environmental consequences of the project. The rap song of the industrialists Diox, Tox and Rob glorify the Megawatt:

Let me tell you a story about Megawatt,

It's a big bucks project we love a lot, Hunh, hunh.

Megawatt, Megawatt, rah, rah, rah,

If you're really good we'll give some stock to you Hunh, hunh.

I said M-E-G-A-W-A and a double yah, a double Tee

It's the biggest money maker for the movers and the shakers in all of history.
Hunh (72).

The saga of Thomas and Lubna, is an effective rendering of the revelation of man's inhumanity to man and nature. Thomas, seduced by the vision of glamorous life promised by the Whites is excited at the idea of getting a job in the Megawatt project. Unable to earn a livelihood due to his nativity, he wishes to make hay while the sun shines. He declares his intention to Lubna:

Remember the time you applied for the job in the bar . . . who got it Lubna, the Indian? No. It was either Maria the Italian, Holly, the Irish girl or Maria France, the French Canadian. It's never us. We're always the last ones. We always get the short end of the stick. Now we finally have an opportunity to move up, and I am not going to miss it (76).

Discarding the much cherished age-old spiritual beliefs of yesteryears, Thomas wishes to join the world of progress and work for self-improvement. Thomas wants Lubna to assimilate herself into the mainstream society. Lubna, very proud of her own soil and culture can never fit into Whiteman's shoes. She lives in close communion with nature that imparts great wisdom and teaches her the art of living. The Natives regard Nature as the Scripture of their lives.

Motherhood, the most sublime form of feminity makes women wholesome. Lubna is in seventh heaven when she learns that she is pregnant. But her happiness is short lived. Dr.Karuna Cate confirms Lubna's pregnancy but to her dismay she finds unusually high levels of mercury in her blood report. Karuna laments, "I found that every two patients out of three who live at the mouth of the river and derive their fish diet from it, are showing signs of mercury poisoning" (81).

The eco-terrorists with their avarice have succeeded in colonizing even the baby in the womb. Lubna is heartbroken when she listens to the mourning of her own child in the womb who questions her about its disabled condition. Lubna's disabled child is the gift of the megawatt. When a deformed, disabled or dead baby is born due to environmental or industrial damages, it is an infringement of human rights and on justice. Thomas blames her, "You're trying to make me feel guilty/ This is not. You had a hand in this too. You were told not to eat the fish. Why did you eat fish? Why didn't you stop eating fish?" (92). Thomas does not want a child that may be disabled or poisoned. Thomas fears that the child will grow up hating him all his life. Thomas expresses his agony. "All my life, I've worked to leave behind the fear – the fear of despair, the fear of my ancestor's past - the fear of uncertainty. And now when I'm to be a father, I have to live in fear of the uncertainty of my own child. No! I can't. You could have"(95).

Lubna has become an environmental refugee. She feels that her fate is akin to the destiny of nature because both are devastated by patriarchal forces. In “The Ecofeminism: Linking Theory and Practice,” Birkeland defines ecofeminism as:

. . . value system, a social movement, and a practice... (which) also offers a political analysis that explores the links between androcentrism and environmental destruction. It is an “awareness” that begins with the realization that the exploitation of nature is intimately linked to Western Man’s attitude toward women and tribal culture. (18)

Lubna is not prepared to destroy her child. She gives vent to her heart’s agony to mother Earth, “I am not performing my most sacred duty. I don’t feed my child a mother’s milk. I feed him mercury. It’s in my blood . . . my milk (96). Women and nature share a divine communion since time immemorial. Susan Griffin, in *Women and Nature: The Roaring Inside Her* states “He says that woman speaks with nature. That she hears voices from under the earth. That wind blows in her ears and trees whisper to her. That the dead sing through her mouth and the cries of infants are clear to her” (45). Lubna is shattered to pieces when she realizes that the baby in her womb is no more. The baby does not wish to come to this darkling plain which is polluted and contaminated to the core. During moments of her emotional turmoil, Mother Earth becomes her guardian angel and fairy godmother who guides her, “Hopes live while people die. Why not live when you’re alive?” (97). Karuna cannot imagine that a conversation can take place between Earth and Lubna. Lubna highlights the significance of Native spirituality , “You may not hear but she talks and we talk back. Your people don’t talk to us but the earth does” (97). The earth and the Natives thus become victims of imperial oppression.

Varma resorts to the technique of anthropomorphism, making Mother Earth voice forth the hazards of environmental destruction. She becomes an important character and the agony of mother earth is indeed heart rending. She mourns her fate, the blow given to here by greedy men with myopic vision. By manipulating the flow of the river with bulldozers, they are taking the earth away and will not leave anything for the children. Mother Earth feels that the Whites are breaking her back:

I am the Earth, the mother. Today I am struck by men of greed and with myopic visions. They gather in their corporate rooms, in pious garbs and recruit the innocent and command strike. Like maniacs they do. They manipulate the flow of the river will bulldozers and backhoes, drowning tons of rocks and soil where from time immemorial the beaver had ruled. Don’t you realize that taking the earth away won’t leave anything – not even for your own children. So you think rivers can wash away your industrial sins. Why don’t you listen? I’m your mother, Earth. Step on a crack, break your Mother’s back. Step on a crack, break your Mother’s back. Step on a crack; break your Mother’s back (75).

While the period of colonialism has faded, imperial dominance remains pervasive. Racial inequality and environmental damage persist in every corner of the earth. There is a global outcry for the conservation of nature. However, the actuality is characterised by the ruthless devastation of the natural world. The environment is contaminated due to mankind's cruelty and frantic pursuit of industrialization and technical progress. Varma's drama portrays a dystopian scenario in which future generations are destined to endure immense suffering. We have received the Earth as an inheritance from our predecessors and it is not within our rights to deprive future generations of it. However, contemporary individuals have ruthlessly devastated the natural world for their self-centered agendas and extravagant lifestyles. The accumulation of e-wastes, which contaminate the environment, is a direct consequence of the intellectual efforts of modern individuals in achieving technological progress. Over time, the planet will accumulate an increasing amount of non-biodegradable waste, turning into a vast pool of refuse. Varma's writing is a thought-provoking piece that aims to raise awareness among readers about the significant issue that looms over them, resembling the threat of a Damocles sword. It is expected that the current generation would make a concerted effort to establish a pristine environment, ensuring that future generations can flourish in a tranquil and uncontaminated planet.

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